

EDUCATION AND INTERCULTURAL DIALOGUE AT NICOLAE FILIMON

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7463523

Mihaela MARCU

Associate Professor, Ph.D., CCCSEM, University of Craiova, Romania,
mihaela_marcu2007@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The contact between cultures, a form of knowledge and permanent communication, was of great concern to the Romanian scholars of the 19th century. They travel around the world, especially in the West, get to know new places, people, customs, establish an intercultural dialogue necessary for the Romanian countries of that period. One such writer is Nicolae Filimon who writes a travel memoir entitled *Escursiuni în Germania meridională. Memorii artistice, istorice și critice* (1858), result of his European trip in the summer of 1858.

Our approach wants to highlight the novelty elements that this travelogue brings. They were necessary for the development of Romanian culture and civilization and can be considered as part of an intercultural dialogue.

KEYWORDS: interculturality, education, dialogue.

1. NICOLAE FILIMON, TRAVELER THROUGH EUROPE

A man of his time, permeated by the bohemian spirit of Bucharest life, Nicolae Filimon was a picturesque character. Among his assiduous concerns is the pleasure of knowledge, of deciphering the mystery of books, of speaking as many foreign languages as possible, in a word, of having as vast a culture as possible.

He proved his talent for writing, first, in the publishing field, printing in December 1857, a musical foil in the first issue of the *Naționalul* newspaper. His journalistic activity was intense, carried out with great dedication and manifested by the publication of musical and theatrical chronicles of the three popular fairy tales in various newspapers of the time. Even the short story *Nenorocirile unui slujnicar sau Gentilomii de mahala* appeared for the first time in the

Revista Carpaților, in 1861. Filimon's representative work, the novel *Ciocoii vechi și noi sau Ce naște din piscă șoareci mănâncă* was published between 1862/1863, initially in folieton, then in volume. The reception of this book by the writer's contemporaries was extremely favorable. However, the generations that succeeded him proved reluctant, sensing the lack of analytical depth at the level of building human characters or highlighting the schematic moralism of the book.

Filimon's writings revealed a trained writer, a painter of his time, a man of culture, who, before the novel *Ciocoii vechi și noi*, had traveled through the West, first of all, out of a desire to know places with old and rich musical traditions. This is how his travel impressions are born, for which he builds a public, informative destination. Hence the wealth of historical data, names of countries, historical monuments, all contained in genuine travel guides, which could always be useful to those interested in that part of the world. At the same time, as we will develop in the next sub-chapter, Nicolae Filimon does not forget the literary aspect and inserts into the memorial romantic stories, spirited evocations, in a word, pages of fiction.

2. ESCURSIUNI ÎN GERMANIA MERIDIONALĂ, ANOTHER KIND OF TRAVEL JOURNAL

Nicolae Filimon's travel memorial, *Excursiuni în Germania meridională. Memorii artistice, istorice și critice* (1858), result of his European trip in the summer of 1858, takes shape only two years after the beginning of the publishing activity. Writing belongs to romanticism by cultivating the passion for travel, an orientation that is gaining more and more popularity in Romanian countries, during the 19th century. Romanian scholars feel impelled to travel abroad, especially to the European West, to get to know each other, to make comparisons, to convey impressions, emotions, feelings to their compatriots. The voices of the world had to be deciphered, assumed and then communicated to the public eager to assimilate information about the European way of existence, about the customs and historical facts of other peoples, about the beauties of nature in other countries

Nicolae Filimon's book is part of a tradition of travelogues from the 19th century. It is not known whether Filimon knew the diaries of his predecessors, travelers on the roads of Europe, nor is it important. It remains relevant that through the work *Excursions in Southern Germany*, this new genre in Romanian literature gains depth. It is certain that Nicolae Filimon was stimulated by the typical travel diaries published in the press of the time in the country, but especially from abroad. Anyway, he is part of a tradition that has become, from now on, part of

literature, and permanent reporting to predecessors, as well as to contemporaries, becomes necessary.

Nicolae Filimon's travel notes are born as a result of a trip undertaken by the writer through various European cities, a trip attributed to the desire to get to know places with old artistic and musical traditions. Thus he visits Pesta, Vienna, Prague, Dresden, Munich, Kissingen, in Italy he sees Venice, Rome, Florence, Pisa, Genoa, Milan, Bergamo, Padua. It seems that Filimon was also driven on this journey by the need to know, and probably to re-know, the world known from books, to live the feeling of the authentic, to stimulate, by comparison with others, his own and intellectual life.

Therefore, "unlike Dinicu Golescu's diary, serious, genuine, modestly limited to his own experiences and impressions, Nicolae Filimon's diary is constructed with full care for the public purpose of such writing. Filimon wants, first of all, to appear well-informed. That's why they string dry, historical data, monuments, paintings, transcripts from tourist guides, museum catalogs, from a work on the history of art by Cesare Cantu. On the other hand, a city, a place, a circumstance inspires him with stormy evocations, romantic stories included in the memorial, some of which are then resumed as independent writings. When freed from bookishness and romantic affectation, travel notations have nerve and charm. Then the real Filimon appears, sharp, penetrating, a man full of comic verve or subtle irony. The comparison pages between the states at home and those abroad outline the social observer, the moralist. They indicate the influence of Pashoptist political thinking on this writer who seemed to have isolated himself from revolutionary aspects"(DLR, p. 352).

Nicolae Filimon's accounts are natural, free of inhibitions, of the complex of the man who came from a small country, but who knows how to assimilate what he sees in the foreign spaces traveled. Filimon's documentation before his western journey is complex: he familiarizes himself with the European cities that became landmarks of his journey either from the tourist guides published in the era, or from the books or newspapers he read. Here is added the wealth of knowledge about historical facts from ancient times to the present, about cultural, mythological facts, knowledge that Nicolae Filimon had acquired from school instruction or from his self-taught training. All this, gathered, transforms the Romanian writer's impressions and comments into a fact of worldliness, the author gaining the freedom to express not only his enthusiasm, but also a sustained critical attitude. There is no lack of his own positioning, real and realistic, in receiving and evaluating what he sees, what he knows. An example of the Romanian traveler's critical attitude towards a foreign reality is, among others, the moment of live contact with Wagner's music, a reflection of his training as a music critic.

Nicolae Filimon's travel impressions open another literary era, undoubtedly modern, as Aurel Martin remarks, who places his work in the category of *frontier literature*. If Dinicu Golescu reproduces the type of enlightened traveler, Alecsandri or Bolintineanu compose the sphere of the romantic traveler, Ion Codru Drăgușanu is the scholarly pilgrim, Nicolae Filimon is placed, as in a game of mirrors, in the category of "frontier literature", which he represents the most eloquent.

In Filimon's memorial, the pleasure of reverie is combined with the desire to know, to learn, the author fulfilling several roles at the same time: he is a reporter, pamphleteer, writer. Apparently calculated in order to save time and money, the European itinerary of the Romanian scholar deviates from the fixed landmarks, improvises escapades not included in the program. Instead of participating in the bourgeois parties to which he was invited, Filimon prefers to visit museums, theaters, and historical monuments with his notebook in hand. "Man is jovial par excellence, and the journey in his case is neither an exodus nor an escape, let alone a fight with shadows. Filimon is spared the conscience problems of a Dinicu Golescu, the frustrations of Bolintineanu or the resentments and emphasis of Heliade. His profession of tourist faith, full of common sense and no frills, is detached from both romantic solipsism and the virtuous austerity of the lights"(Filimon, *Escursiuni*, p. 310).

The intention of the traveler is to inform the reader about what he visited, from as many angles as possible. From here, the frequent interruptions of the writing with historical references, with concrete data that fall into the category of statistics. But above all, Nicolae Filimon, reflexive and organized, expresses, on every occasion, his personal opinion, the impression caused, looks for explanations, becomes polemical, witty, ironic. "Completely alien to the strategy of the modern writer, who prefers to blur his ideological discourse, operating through suggestion and allusive formulas, Filimon clearly manifests his convictions. Of course, he wants to persuade his reader, because he feels his responsibility as an enlightener and a militant. All the more so as it is my opinion that here as in other places, the public is exactly like a child without knowledge, who comes to school to learn" (Ibidem, p.311).

We are greeted in numerous pages of this travel diary by an unexpected method of epicizing the facts, a remarkable ability to make any discussion, any meeting an opportunity to introduce an anecdote, a narrative. Here the writing talent of Nicolae Filimon becomes obvious.

In fact, in these accounts are inserted real short stories inspired by the dramatic moments of more distant or closer events, which the author takes note of during this journey. An eloquent example is, from this perspective, the 19th chapter entitled *Friedrich Staaps sau Atentatul de la Schonbrunn în contra lui Napoleon I*, which is one of Filimon's "first short stories" under the impression of the steamy romantic journey with a Germany and an illustrated Italy seen as in the narratives of Alexandre Dumas"(Călinescu, ILR, p. 359).

CONCLUSIONS

The travelogue described uses elements of interculturality, such as intercultural education or dialogue. Nicolae Filimon's intentions were to help Romanians, to provide examples, to educate through the power of examples. That is why we can speak of an accumulation of intercultural elements in this writing of the 19th century.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- Călinescu, George, *Istoria literaturii române de la origini până în prezent*, ediția a II-a, revăzută și adăugită, ediție și prefață de Al. Piru, București, Editura Minerva, 1985 (Călinescu, ILR).
- Dicționarul literaturii române de la origini până în anul 1900*, București, Editura Academiei, 1979 (DLR).
- Filimon, Nicolae, *Escursiuni în Germania meridională. Nuvele*, postfață și bibliografie de Paul Cornea, București, Editura Minerva, 1984 (Filimon, *Escursiuni*).